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Investigation of Social Media Usage Status of Music Teacher Candidates

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Abstract

The progress societies take in progress becomes directly proportional to their adaptation to technology and their rapid catching up with change. In the computer age, all kinds of life layers of individuals are intertwined with technology. As a matter of fact, education, culture, health, social and all kinds of social life layers are being carried out through the internet, social networks and technological tools. While the Internet and social media have emerged as an alternative communication medium, they have emerged as an opportunity for individuals who have difficulty expressing themselves especially in the public sphere or in their social circles. Social networks, which provide opportunities for young people to make their voices heard, produce content, create networks by coming together with individuals who think like them, and increase their democratic participation by expressing their opinions on political and social issues, have also had positive effects in this context. This research was conducted to measure the social media usage purposes of music teacher candidates, and to determine whether their social media use purposes, situations and areas are related to social media use disorder or addiction. Social media usage scale were applied to the study group determined by the random assignment method within the scope of the research, and in the light of the data obtained, the social media usage status of the music teacher candidates was compared with the gender and individual instrument variables, and it was examined whether there was a significant difference between them

Keywords: Music Education, Music Teacher Candidates, Internet, Social Media

1. Introduction

Technological changes and developments are now taking place in all areas of daily life. The progress societies take in progress becomes directly proportional to their adaptation to technology and their rapid catching up with change. In the computer age, all kinds of life layers of individuals are intertwined with technology. As a matter of fact, education, culture, health, social and all kinds of social life layers are being carried out through the internet, social networks and technological tools. While the Internet and social media have emerged as an alternative communication medium, they have emerged as an opportunity for individuals who have difficulty expressing themselves especially in the public sphere or in their social circles. Social networks, which provide opportunities for young people to make their voices heard, produce content, create networks by coming together with individuals

who think like them, and increase their democratic participation by expressing their opinions on political and social issues, have also had positive effects in this context.

Today, with the rapid development of communication technologies and the internet, the reflections of technology on social, cultural and economic life are visibly felt. Communication technologies, which are seen as one of the driving dynamics of the rapid changes in society, have also changed the communication habits of the individual in their social life to a certain extent. With this transformative power, technology has begun to adapt individuals and even societies to itself. In other words, this mediated form of communication realized through technology has gradually become widespread in the society, and this has brought about changes in both individual and social communication practices (Aydın, 2016).

Many factors are effective in increasing the importance of social media in society. These factors; It is possible to list them as being easy to use, delivering the desired messages to large audiences quickly, being completely free, and offering two-way communication (Altunbaş and Kul 2015: 415). The effective role of computer and communication technologies in our lives is undeniable. Particularly, thanks to the internet, which is a revolutionary communication technology, instant sharing of different types of data such as videos, music and photos and access to information have become easier. The Internet has created a gigantic environment of computer networks that exist at the same time and everywhere, independent of the physical space and that will unite millions of people in the virtual world (Yılmazsoy and Kahraman, 2017).

Along with the change and development of life styles and technology, communication opportunities, ways of obtaining information, personal development process and content have changed. The social media environment created by the change in the media is a determining factor in the diversification of information, the spread of information, the form of information, access to information and internalization of information (Kamiloğlu and Yurttaş, 2014: 132). According to Menteşe (2013: 13), in the twenty-first century, which is the age of information and technology, information technologies have affected the learning-teaching process, social, economic and cultural life. However, it has also changed the interpersonal interaction, especially the communication style of people, to different dimensions.

Generally; Although it is accepted that social media, which is defined as the set of tools and platforms that people use to share their thoughts, experiences, comprehension skills, perceptions, media such as music, video and photography with each other, has entered our lives in parallel with the development of internet technologies, it is actually seen that its use has become widespread in the 2000s and later (Lai and Turban, 2008). It can be thought of as the desire to eliminate the socialization that cannot be achieved or gained in real life in the virtual environment. The individual tries to socialize through e-mails, chat rooms, discussion forums and online games. An individual who wants to have social interaction via the Internet does not favor face-to-face interaction. The tendency of the individual to socialize or to find social support triggers the risk of internet addiction and the individual may move away from the society (Günüç & Kayri, 2010). Today, on social media sites, a large number of people use their real identity information. They can freely share and discuss a large number of different types of information and disseminate this process. Today, interaction on social networking sites is based on friendship, kinship, interests and activities. But this is not the only function of social networks. These networks consist of not only family and friends, but also teachers, school staff, neighbors, and different circles in the community. Social networks provide users with many opportunities such as creating and sharing information, establishing and developing relationships (Kwon & Wen, 2010).

Social media tools are rapidly diversifying and constantly evolving. This situation has made the use of social media tools in education increasingly important (Kocadere & Aşkar, 2013). The use of social media tools in education will also strengthen the communication between students and teachers. It is an undeniable fact that children born in the 21st century are constantly exposed to these tools from the moment they are born. According to Öztürk and Talas (2015), thanks to the worldwide spread of social media applications, people have gone far beyond communicating with people in the same neighborhood or in the same city. The ability of people to communicate with each other globally has started a new era (Güney, 2018). Today, interpersonal communication with internet-based applications is very common. Not only text messages, but also different kinds of messages appealing to many sense organs such as photographs, videos, and voices are communicated. Social media is very common in

these relationships established between people over the internet with a computer or mobile phone (Kırık, Pepeler, & Özbek, 2018).

With the Internet becoming an interactive world with Web 2.0, cooperation through social networks enables information sharing and production between educators and those who prepare the information (universities) (Strathdee, 2007) and is used to support education (Cited by Yılmazsoy and Kahraman, 2017). On the other hand, according to Cemaloğlu and Bıçak (2015), social networking sites, the use of which are becoming more and more widespread in the information age we live in, lead teachers and students, who are indispensable elements of schools, to an active participation in social networks and rapidly increase teacher-student interaction (Gül and Diken, 2018). One of the factors affecting the media literacy levels of teacher candidates is the purpose of using social networking sites. Social networking sites have become one of the ways of communication that people from all segments of society use intensively (Ulu and Baş, 2020). Social Media Agency has determined that individuals spend an average of two hours a day on social networks. The country that spends the most time is Argentina with 4.3 hours, and the country that spends the least time is Japan with 0.8 hours. Turkey has gained a place above the average with 2.5 hours (Dal and Dal, 2014).

When the literature is examined, it is seen that different scientific researches of academicians in this field are related to the effects of social media usage status, internet addiction status and social media usage status of university students and teacher candidates studying in different departments. Baş and Dikbaş (2020), Bilgici et al. (2016), Demir and Kumcagiz (2019), Erdem et al. (2017), Erol et al. (2021), Güler et al. (2019), Karasu and Arıkan (2016), Koçer (2012), Özalp and Akpınar (2018), Rıdvan and Yıldırım (2016), Somyürek and Gün (2017), Tavşanlı and Akaydın (2017), Tekin and Erdoğan (2020), Varol and Yıldırım (2017) and Yayla (2018) carried out scientific researches related to the use of social media by pre-service teachers.

This research is aimed at “Does the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to various variables?” structured around the research question. In the study, the social media usage status of the music teacher candidates was compared with the gender and individual instrument variables they were studying, and it was tried to reveal whether there were significant differences between the social media usage status and the variables. In the research, answers to the following sub-research questions were sought in the focus of the main research question;

1. What is the distribution of music teacher candidates' daily social media usage times and social media preferences?
2. How are the social media usage tools and purposes of music teacher candidates distributed?
3. Does the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to their gender?
4. Does the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to the individual instrument types they are studying?

This research was conducted to measure the social media usage purposes and social media addiction levels of music teacher candidates, and to determine whether their social media use purposes, situations and areas are related to social media use disorder or addiction. In the literature, the limited number of scientific studies on the use of social media by music teacher candidates is considered important in terms of revealing the social media literacy, use cases, aims and effects and contributions of music teacher candidates on their education, identifying the problems, if any, arising from the use of social media, and offering solutions.

This research is limited to;

1. With the fall and spring semesters of the 2021-2022 academic year,
2. With the music teacher candidates studying in the departments of fine arts education, music education program of the education faculties of the universities in the study group in the 2021-2022 academic year,
3. Music teacher candidates who are in the study group, who are studying in the relevant departments and who also use the internet and social media.

2. Method

2.1 Model of the Research

This research is a descriptive study using the relational screening model, which aims to examine the social media usage status of music teacher candidates. The research model that aims to determine the existence of change between two or more variables or the degree of this change is called the relational survey model (Karasar, 2017). In survey models, there are observations of science, detecting relationships between events, and reaching generalizations on controlled invariant relationships. In other words, the descriptive function of science is in the foreground (Yıldırım, 1966). Kaya (2012) explains that, in the descriptive-correlational survey model, a study determines a situation or event as it is and finds out relationships, effects, and degrees of the variables causing this situation or event. Gürbüz and Şahin (2017 p.108) state that the correlational survey model is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and any significant differences in certain variables, and also announced that the causes of the relation are sought by using correlation, regression, and difference tests. A researcher working with the scanning model should not only directly examine what he is researching, but also consult the previously kept records about the researched thing, the resource people related to that field, and integrate his own observations with what he has obtained. Recording the events as they are in the scanning model is the most important feature. However, comments and evaluations are mandatory. The scanning model serves these two purposes (Yıldırım, 1966).

2.2 Research Assumptions

1. The participants were assumed to give sincere answers to the measurement tool used in the data collection within the research.
2. The music teacher candidates were assumed to participate in the study voluntarily and were in mental health to respond to the scale questions.

2.3 Study Group

The study group of the research consists of music teacher candidates who are studying in the fall and spring semesters of the 2021-2022 academic year in the department of fine arts education, affiliated to the education faculties of 6 universities, which are determined by the random assignment method, and who are also internet and social media users. Below is the demographic information of the music teacher candidates participating in the research in the relevant departments of the universities that make up the study group and in the relevant departments;

1. Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Muğla)
2. Pamukkale University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Denizli)
3. Cumhuriyet University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Sivas)
4. Harran University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Şanlıurfa)
5. Trabzon University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Trabzon)
6. Trakya University, Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education, Music Education Program (Edirne)

The data on the gender of the music teacher candidates in the study group and the individual instruments they are studying are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Distribution of the Music Teacher Candidates to whom the Scale was Applied by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	73	35
Female	139	65

Total	212	100,0
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Looking at Table 1, 65% of the 212 music teacher candidates to whom the scale was applied are female and 35% male.

Table 2: Distribution of Music Teacher Candidates to whom the Scale was Applied by Individual Instrument Types

Individual Instrument	Frequency	Percentage
String Instruments	86	41,0
Wind Instruments	53	25,0
Clavier Instruments	46	22,0
Picks Instruments	27	12,0
Total	212	100,0

2.4 Data Collection Tools

The "Social media usage purposes scale" developed by Solmaz et al. (2013) was used as a data collection tool in the research. The social media usage scale, which was developed to determine the social media usage status of teacher candidates, consists of 11 items. The standardized loads of the scale were between 0.57 and 0.60, and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.703. In addition, the individual instruments and genders of 212 music teacher candidates, who were applied a scale to determine whether the social media usage status of the music teacher candidates differ according to the variables, were also collected through the personal data form. Before proceeding to the data collection process of the research, necessary ethical permissions were obtained from Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University Human Research Ethics Commission-2 with the report numbered 14 on 05.11.2021. After obtaining the necessary ethical permission, the data collection phase of the research was started. The data used within the scope of the research were collected face-to-face and via google form in the fall and spring semesters of the 2021-2022 academic year.

2.5 Analysis of Data

Research data were analyzed with SPSS 22 package program. Descriptive statistics were used for the first and second sub-research questions of the study. Independent sample t-test was used to determine the relationship between social media usage status of music teacher candidates and gender variables related to the third sub-research question of the study. One-Factor Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to determine the relationship between the social media usage status of music teacher candidates, which is the third sub-research question of the study, and the variables of individual instrument type they are studying.

3. Results

3.1 Results of the First Sub-Research Question

The first sub-research question of the study, "How is the distribution of music teacher candidates' daily social media usage times and social media preferences?" Findings related to the question are given below.

Table 3: Distribution of Music Teacher Candidates to whom the Scale was Applied on Daily Social Media Usage Periods

Daily Usage Time	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 Hour	12	05,7
1-1,5 Hours	27	12,7

2-2.5 Hours	51	24,5
3-3,5 Hours	54	25,0
4-4,5 Hours	23	10,8
More than 4.5 Hours	45	21,3
Total	212	100,0

According to Chart 3, 25% of the 212 music teacher candidates to whom the scale was applied use social media for an average of 3-3.5 hours a day, 24.5% of them for 2-2.5 hours, 21.3% of them used social media for more than 4,5 hours, 12.7 of them used social media for 1-1.5 hours, 10.8 of them 4-4.5 hours and 5.7 of them for less than 1 hour daily average finding has been reached. According to this; It can be said that the majority of the music teacher candidates to whom the scale was applied spend more than 2 hours a day on social media.

Table 4: Distribution of Preferred Social Media Platform of Music Teacher Candidates to Which Scale was Applied

Preferred Social Media Platform	Frequency	Percentage
Instagram	98	45,0
Twitter	45	22,0
Facebook	21	10,0
Tiktok	13	06,0
Youtube	28	14,0
Skype	07	03,0
Total	212	100,0

According to Chart 4 it has been found that 45% of the 212 music teacher candidates to whom the scale was applied preferred instagram as their social media platform, 22% twitter, 14% youtube, 10% facebook, 6% tik tok and 3% preferred the skype social media platform. According to this; It can be said that the most preferred social media platforms by the music teacher candidates to whom the scale was applied are Instagram, Twitter and YouTube.

3.2 Results of the Second Sub-Research Question

The first sub-research question of the study, "How is the distribution of music teacher candidates' daily social media usage times and social media preferences?" findings related to the question are given below.

Table 5: Distribution of Music Teacher Candidates to Which Scale was Applied on Social Media Usage Tools

Social Media Usage Tools	Frequency	Percentage
Mobil Phone	120	56,0
Tablet	43	20,0
Laptop	12	06,0
Desktop Computer	37	18,0
Total	212	100,0

When Table 5 was examined, it was found that 56% of 212 music teacher candidates, who applied the scale, preferred mobile phone as a social media usage tool, 20% preferred tablet, 18% preferred laptop and the remaining 6% preferred desktop computer. In the light of these findings, it was determined that more than half of the music

teacher candidates, who applied the scale, prefer mobile phone as a social media usage tool, although they also use computer and tablet as a social media usage and it can be said to have been selected that mobile phone is commonly used as a tool to usage social media.

Table 6: The Distribution of Music Teacher Candidates Regarding the Purposes of Social Media Use of the Scale

Social Media Usage Purposes	Frequency	Percentage
For Listen to Music	93	43,0
For Know to News	44	20,0
For Enjoy	27	14,0
For Follow the Trend	18	08,0
For Spend Time	30	15,0
Total	212	100,0

According to Chart 6, 43% of 212 music teacher candidates, who were applied scale, used social media for listening to music, 20% for know to news, 15% for spend time, 14% for enjoying and the remaining 8% for follow the trend. The data that they use social media to according to this, it can be said that the music teacher candidates, to whom the scale was applied, mainly use social media for listen to music, communicate and evaluate their spend time.

3.3 Results of the Third Sub-Research Question

The third sub-research question of the study, "Does the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to their gender?" Findings related to the question are given below.

Table 7: Distribution of Social Media Usage Status of Music Teacher Candidates to whom the Scale was Applied by Gender Variable

Social Media Usage Scale	Gender	f	$\bar{x}$	ss	p
I use social media to communicate with friends	Male	73	3,44	,957	,361
	Female	139	3,57	,959	,362
I use social media for fun and relaxation	Male	73	2,63	,881	,039*
	Female	139	2,41	,913	,037*
I use social media to spend my free time	Male	73	3,24	,954	,230
	Female	139	3,41	,931	,234
I use social media to listen music	Male	73	3,56	1,117	,194
	Female	139	3,76	1,039	,205
I use social media to send and receive messages	Male	73	3,36	1,060	,154
	Female	139	3,58	1,013	,161
I use social media to get to know people better	Male	73	2,65	1,169	,019*
	Female	139	2,39	1,100	,016*
I use social media to follow events or trends	Male	73	4,00	,903	,154
	Female	139	3,81	,897	,155
I use social media for personal presentation and information sharing	Male	73	3,04	1,072	,386
	Female	139	2,91	,981	,399
I use social media to reach people and organizations	Male	73	3,13	,923	,430
	Female	139	3,02	,977	,422
I use social media to exchange ideas	Male	73	3,94	1,006	,618
	Female	139	3,96	1,103	,608
I use social media to access information	Male	73	2,47	,944	,015*
	Female	139	2,68	,992	,024*

* $p < ,05$

According to Table 7, when the averages of the social media usage scale sub-dimensions applied to the music teacher candidates were examined, it was found that social media was most frequently used to follow the events/agenda among the music teacher candidates, and that social media was mostly used for the exchange of ideas. On the contrary, it was found that music teacher candidates use social media to access information, to get to know people better, and to have fun and relax. When Table 7 is examined, according to the findings obtained from the independent sample t-test applied to determine whether the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to gender, the gender of the music teacher candidates and the sub-dimension of using social media for fun and relaxation, and the sub-dimension of using social media to get to know people better. It has been found that there is a significant difference between the sub-dimensions of using social media for access to information. It can be said that according to findings, male music teacher candidates use social media more for fun and relaxation than female music teacher candidates, male music teacher candidates use social media more often than female music teacher candidates to get to know people better, female music teacher candidates use social media compared to male music teacher candidates.

3.4 Results on the Fourth Sub-Research Question

The fourth sub-research question of the study, "Does the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differ according to the individual instruments they are studying?" findings related to the question are given below.

Table 8: Distribution of Social Media Usage Status of Music Teacher Candidates to which Scale was Applied by Individual Instrument Variable

Social Media Usage Scale	Individual Ins.	f	$\bar{x}$	ss	p
I use social media to communicate with friends	Strings	83	3,25	,7112	,593
	Winds	51	3,26	1,165	,030*
	Claviers	48	2,93	,7054	,000*
	Picks	30	3,11	,8690	,001*
I use social media for fun and relaxation	Strings	83	3,60	,6578	,593
	Winds	51	3,07	,7591	,528
	Claviers	48	2,71	,9498	,002*
	Picks	30	3,24	1,035	,646
I use social media to spend my free time	Strings	83	3,13	,8719	,195
	Winds	51	2,74	,7163	,585
	Claviers	48	3,22	,9662	,038*
	Picks	30	3,49	1,065	,033*
I use social media to listen music	Strings	83	2,97	1,199	,530
	Winds	51	2,68	1,201	,197
	Claviers	48	2,93	1,032	,810
	Picks	30	3,22	1,094	,530
I use social media to send and receive messages	Strings	83	2,99	,9661	1,00
	Winds	51	3,31	1,134	,969
	Claviers	48	3,23	,8870	,009*
	Picks	30	3,54	,8703	1,00
I use social media to get to know people better	Strings	83	3,46	,8804	,782
	Winds	51	3,24	,7132	,013*
	Claviers	48	2,63	,7539	,769
	Picks	30	3,20	,8703	,981
I use social media to follow events or trends	Strings	83	2,20	,7869	1,00
	Winds	51	1,91	,6176	,609

	Claviers	48	1,84	,5514	,817
	Picks	30	2,03	,7799	1,00
I use social media for personal presentation and information sharing	Strings	83	3,65	,8325	,981
	Winds	51	3,86	,7647	,713
	Claviers	48	3,24	,8333	,969
	Picks	30	3,53	,8924	,981
I use social media to reach people and organizations	Strings	83	2,64	,9841	,003*
	Winds	51	2,76	,9581	,030*
	Claviers	48	2,35	,8255	,730
	Picks	30	2,74	,9837	,941
I use social media to exchange ideas	Strings	83	2,72	,7361	,013*
	Winds	51	2,78	,7546	,528
	Claviers	48	2,71	,7514	,002*
	Picks	30	2,76	,7789	,942
I use social media to access information	Strings	83	3,06	,8471	,023*
	Winds	51	3,10	,8723	,527
	Claviers	48	2,63	,7504	,063
	Picks	30	3,00	,8112	,033*

* p<,05

When Table 8 is examined, it has been found that the social media usage status of music teacher candidates differs according to the individual instrument types they are studying. The sub-dimensions of the social media usage scale were compared with the individual instrument types of 212 pre-service music teachers, and the data in table 8 were obtained. According to this; In the sub-dimension of using social media for communication with their friends, it was found that there was a significant difference between the individual instrument types of the music teacher candidates, to whom the scale was applied. It can be said that the music teacher candidates who receive wind, key and plectrum training apart from the string instruments group use social media mostly for communication with their friends compared to the music teacher candidates in the string instruments group. When the data of the sub-dimension of using social media to relax are examined, it can be said that the music teacher candidates in the key instruments group often use social media to relax, while the music teacher candidates studying in the string, wind and plectrum group rarely use social media to relax. It was found that there were significant differences between the sub-dimension of using social media to evaluate leisure time and the individual instrument types of music teacher candidates. It can be said that the music teacher candidates who are trained in the keyboard and plectrum instrument type often use social media for the purpose of evaluating their spare time, while the music teacher candidates in the string and wind instrument group rarely use social media for leisure. Again, a significant difference was determined between the sub-dimension of using social media for the purpose of sending or receiving messages and the variable of types of instruments. It can be said that they use the media to receive or send messages. Again, in the light of the data obtained from Table 8, it was determined that there were significant differences between the sub-dimension of using social media to get to know people better and the individual instrument variable. While music teacher candidates who are studying woodwind instruments mostly use social media to get to know people better, it can be said that music teacher candidates in the string, key and plectrum group rarely use social media to get to know people. Significant differences were found between the sub-dimension of using social media to reach people and organizations and the variable of instrument type. It can be said that while the music teacher candidates studying in the string and wind instrument type often use social media to reach people and organizations, it can be said that the music teacher candidates studying in the keyboard and plectrum type instrument rarely use social media to reach people and organizations. When the sub-dimension of using social media for the exchange of ideas is examined, it can be said that the music teacher candidates in the string instruments and key instruments group mostly use social media for the exchange of ideas, while the music teacher candidates in the wind instruments and plectrum group rarely use social media for the exchange of ideas. It was also found that there were differences between the last sub-dimension, the sub-dimension of using social media to access information, and the individual instrument variables of the music teacher candidates. Accordingly, it can be said that while the music teacher candidates in the string instruments and plectrum group use socially frequently

for access to information, the music teacher candidates in the wind instruments and key instrument group rarely use social media for access to information.

4. Discussion

In the light of the findings, most of the music teacher candidates spend more than 2 hours a day on social media, the most preferred social media platforms of music teacher candidates are instagram, twitter and youtube, and more than half of the music teacher candidates prefer mobile phones as a social media tool. Although it has been determined that they also use computers and tablets as social media usage tools, they are not preferred as much as mobile phones, mobile phones are widely chosen as a means of using social media, and music teacher candidates use social media mainly to listen to music, communicate and spend their spare time. used results were obtained. Deniz and Coşkun, (2004), Durmuş and Başarmak, (2014), Sırakaya and Seferoğlu, (2013) Tektaş (2014), Solmaz et al. (2013), Özalp and Akpınar (2018), Erol et al. (2021) with research have obtained similar results.

It has been determined that there is a significant difference between the gender of music teacher candidates and the sub-dimension of using social media for fun and relaxation, sub-dimension of using social media to get to know people better, and sub-dimensions of using social media for access to information. According to this; Male music teacher candidates use social media more for fun and relaxation than female music teacher candidates, male music teacher candidates use social media more often than female music teacher candidates to get to know people better, female music teacher candidates use social media compared to male music teacher candidates. It has been concluded that they use more information-oriented access. While the result that teacher candidates' social media usage status differs according to gender variables is also seen in Koçer, (2012) and Yayla's (2018) studies, it was concluded in Yeşiltaş's (2016) research that teacher candidates' social media usage did not differ according to gender variable.

In the light of the findings about whether the social media usage status of the music teacher candidates differ according to the individual instrument types they are studying, it was concluded that the social media usage status of the 212 music teacher candidates who were applied the scale differs according to the individual instrument types they are studying. In their research, Lei et al. (2021) found that music students from different instrument groups have some drawbacks in using social media, that they may experience problems in instrument development and intonation, and that music students from eight different instruments may encounter different problems in their use of social media.

In parallel with the results obtained from the research, music teacher candidates can provide conscious, useful, necessary self-control in their use of social media, and can provide the necessary controls themselves in line with the awareness of the power of use of the internet and social media. In today's information and technology age, in line with the use of the internet and social media, the necessary infrastructure, equipment and materials can be prepared in educational institutions in line with the use of technological tools by educators with their educational aspects and using them in educational activities, in-service trainings on the use of technology in education can be benefited, and educators can be informed in the context of technological innovations. Considering in parallel with the distance education activities that emerged after the pandemic, social media can be used more frequently in online education, and all kinds of communication tools brought by technology can be used in an educational context. Considering the positive impact, development and contribution of art, music and education on the individual, people can be directed to musical, artistic and educational activities from social media and internet and social media platforms, which are assumed to lead individuals from being introverted and socializing to individualization.

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